

Association of Cigarette Smoking and Raised Blood Cholesterol Levels in Young Population Attending Outpatient Department of a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract

Background and Objectives: According to the WHO, India is home to 12% of the world's smokers. More than 1 million die each year due to tobacco in India. Cigarette smoking is one of the most extensively used potentially hazardous social habits throughout the world. The study was aimed to determine the deleterious effects of smoking on lipid profile and to study association between lipid profile and smoking.

Material and Method: The study was conducted on 150 normal asymptomatic healthy males. Out of which 75 were controls and 75 were cigarette smokers with age-group between 17-35 years. The association of cigarette smoking and raised blood cholesterol levels was studied. Smokers and non-smokers who attended the outpatient clinic as a patient, attendant, volunteer and staff were recruited in the study. The subjects enrolled for the study were informed about the study and procedural details and an informed consent was obtained. In order to exclude conditions that might influence the results, the recruitment of subject was done on the basis of following criteria. They were all vegetarians, belonged to the age group of 17 to 35 years, indulged in equivalent physical exercise and did not consume alcohol. Patient suffering from chronic diseases or taking medications for lipid lowering were excluded.

Results: The study showed, cigarette had raised concentration of serum total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL-cholesterol, VLDL-cholesterol and had reduced levels of HDL cholesterol. Mean cholesterol, LDL, Triglycerides levels were increased with the severity of smoking which was found to be significant while level of HDL decreases with severity which was also statistically significant. ($p < 0.05$)

Conclusion: We observed a dose response relationship between the number of cigarettes smoked and cardiovascular morbidity and mortality.

Keywords: Cigarette Smoking, Cholesterol, Atherosclerosis, Dyslipidemia, Morbidity.

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Introduction

Tobacco smoking is the act of inhaling particle- and gas-phased tobacco smoke after smoking tobacco. In many developing

nations, tobacco use in various forms is a frequent addiction among the socioeconomically disadvantaged people.

[1] An estimate from the WHO from 2002 states that 30% of adult males in India smoke. The percentage among adult females is substantially smaller, at 3-5%. Nearly every organ in the body suffers damage from tobacco use, which also increases the risk of disease and lowers smokers' overall health. [2,3]

South East Asia has a far higher prevalence of cigarette smoking. India ranked second only to China in terms of the number of adult smokers in 2010 with an estimated 120 million smokers. 10% of all deaths in India in 2010 were attributed to smoking, which resulted in around 1 million deaths. Around 70% of these deaths happened in those between the ages of 30 and 69. [4] Smoking cigarettes has many different effects on cardiovascular disease, including atherosclerosis, or plaque (fatty streaks), which is a slow-moving condition that frequently begins in childhood and worsens with age. Additionally, smoking directly affects platelets, increasing activation and stickiness. As a result, there is a higher risk of thrombosis or the formation of blood clots. [5]

According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), one-third of all deaths from cardiovascular disease are caused by smoking. A significant increase of serum Cholesterol, Triglyceride and Low-density lipoprotein with significant decrease in serum High density lipoprotein level (HDL) has been documented in smokers. The most well-documented impact that smoking has on cholesterol is how it lowers levels of HDL. HDL has protective effects against heart disease, it's particularly beneficial for women, who typically have higher levels of the cholesterol than men. [6] Thus, the study was aimed to determine the deleterious effects of smoking on lipid profile and to study association between lipid profile and smoking.

Material and Methods

A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted on 150 subjects (75 control and 75 smokers) attending the outpatient clinic of the Medicine department of LNCT Medical College & Sewakunj Hospital, Indore after obtaining permission from Institutional Ethics Committee. The study was carried out from August 2022 to January 2023 (6 months).

Smokers and non-smokers who attended the outpatient clinic as a patient, attendant, volunteer and staff were recruited in the study. The subjects enrolled for the study were informed about the study and procedural details and an informed consent was obtained. In order to exclude conditions that might influence the results, the recruitment of subject was done on the basis of following criteria. They were all vegetarians, belonged to the age group of 17 to 35 years, indulged in equivalent physical exercise and did not consume alcohol. Patient suffering from chronic diseases or taking medications for lipid lowering were excluded.

Patients were categorised into mild smokers (1-10 cigarettes per day), moderate smokers (11-20 Cigarettes per day) and sever smokers (> 20 cigarettes per day).

A self-administered questionnaire was used to obtain the demographic data of the participants. All participants provided information on age, family history, personal habits (alcohol intake, tobacco consumption, type and level of physical exercise, drug ingestion, known pathological conditions). In addition, all participants were asked to perform their blood test in fasting condition for at least 12 hours before collecting the blood sample. All blood samples were tested at the hospital laboratory. The investigations were done within 2 hours of collecting blood. Total cholesterol as estimated by the method of Schoenheimer and Sperry modified by Venugopala Rao and Ramakrishnan while HDL cholesterol was analysed by the technique of polyanion precipitation with Heparin and managanous

chloride and estimated as cholesterol in the supernatant.

Statistical Analysis: The recorded observations were put into Epi info software. Data was expressed as mean value \pm standard deviation at corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CIs) and

comparisons between the three groups were performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and unpaired t test was used for comparisons between two groups (smoker and Non- smoker).

Results

Table 1: Anthropometric and Lipid Profile in Smokers and Non- Smokers

Parameters	Smokers (n=75)	Non- Smokers (n=75)	p- value
Age (years)	41.52 \pm 7.20	34.20 \pm 12.68	<0.05*
Weight (kg)	62.08 \pm 10.47	60.20 \pm 10.70	NS
Height (cm)	165.40 \pm 6.22	164.96 \pm 8.80	NS
Cholesterol (mg/dl)	202 \pm 38.32	164 \pm 34.11	<0.05*
LDL (mg/dl)	128.11 \pm 46.71	138.20 \pm 86.11	<0.05*
Triglycerides	192 \pm 78.40	88.10 \pm 38.38	NS
HDL	35.44 \pm 8.90	48.76 \pm 16.20	<0.05*

*P<0.05 is significant, NS- not significant.

As per Table 1 it was clearly seen that Lipid profile of smokers was significantly higher in terms of cholesterol and LDL, while HDL is significantly higher in Non- Smokers. (p<0.05).

Table 2: Comparison of Lipid Profile parameters with Severity of Smoking

Parameters	Mild (n=20)	Moderate (n=27)	Severe (n=28)
Cholesterol	182.22 \pm 12.10*	198.10 \pm 22.20*	220.42 \pm 34.46*
LDL	130.11 \pm 44.67*	134.32 \pm 48.98*	142.48 \pm 48.99*
Triglycerides	188.10 \pm 54.56*	190.34 \pm 52.50*	200.10 \pm 58.98*
HDL	36.34 \pm 4.50*	32.42 \pm 3.32*	28.98 \pm 2.10*

*P<0.05 is significant

As per table 2 mean cholesterol, LDL, Triglycerides levels were increased with the severity of smoking which was found to be significant. While level of HDL decreases with severity which was also statistically significant. (p<0.05)

Discussion

Historically, most of the smoked tobacco in India has been in the form of cigarettes with tobacco wrapped inside a Tendu leaf. Tobacco smoking, raised blood pressure, elevated blood cholesterol, insufficient physical activity, overweight and obesity, poor nutrition, drinking at harmful levels and diabetes are major preventable risk factors for CVD. Toxic products from cigarette smoke, nicotine and carbon monoxide, circulate in the bloodstream, interfering with the efficient working of the endothelium, eliciting blood fat

abnormalities and impairing glucose regulation. Each effect is implicated in the development of atherosclerotic lesions in the arterial walls. These collections narrow the arteries, gradually impairing blood flow and making the arteries harder, less elastic and more liable to rupture and the process leading to atherosclerosis. In the present study, the results showed that the serum level of total cholesterol, triglyceride, LDL-C, were significantly higher in moderate and severe smoker as compared to non-smokers, thereby revealing a direct dose response relationship. Previous studies have reported the same findings that smokers have a higher risk lipid profile than non-smokers [7-9]. On the contrary, a study by Dirican et al. reported that there was no significant difference in lipid profile among smokers and non-smokers. [10]. The mechanism of increase of blood cholesterol

is through an increase of free fatty acids of blood. In smokers, the nicotine ingested stimulates the secretion of catecholamines. These hormones increase the FFA by lipolysis of adipose tissue fat. The FFA reaching the liver are esterified as Triacylglycerol and cholesteryl esters which are secreted into the blood stream as VLDL which gets converted to LDL in circulation. The greater the release of FFA, the greater the levels of LDL and cholesterol. [^{11,12,13}]

Conclusion

It was concluded from the present study that the dose response relationship between cigarettes smoked and increase in the atherogenic parameters and decline in anti-atherogenic parameters.

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References

1. P Ketan, P Paresh, S Saurin, G Vijay. A Study on Effects of Cigarette Smoking on Blood Cholesterol in Young Population of Ahmedabad. *International Journal of Basic & Applied Physiology*. 2014;3(1):106-110.
2. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. The Health Consequences of Smoking—50 Years of Progress: A Report of the Surgeon General. Atlanta: U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, Office on Smoking and Health, 2014.
3. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. How Tobacco Smoke Causes Disease: What It Means to You. Atlanta: U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, Office on Smoking and Health. 2012.
4. Jha P, Jacob B, Gajalakshmi V, et al. A nationally representative case-control study of smoking and death in India. *N Engl J Med*. 2018;358:1137–47.
5. US Department of Health and Human Services. How tobacco smoke causes disease: the biology and behavioral basis for smoking-attributable disease. A report of the US Surgeon General. Atlanta, Georgia: US Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, Office on Smoking and Health, 2014. Available from: <http://www.surgeongeneral.gov/library/tobaccosmoke/report/index.html>
6. <https://www.everydayhealth.com/high-cholesterol/living-with/the-cholesterol-smoking-connection/>
7. Neki NS. Lipid profile in chronic smokersâ A clinical study. *Journal, Indian Academy of Clinical Medicine*. 2015; 3:51-54.
8. Prabha V., Waheeda S., Meriton Stanley A. Effect of Tobacco Smoking on Lipid Profile. *Indian Journal of Applied Research*. 2017; 5:562-564.
9. Ratnam PK., Kataraki P., Vontela AR. Comparison of Lipid Profile in Smokers and Non-Smokers in and around Nalgonda, Andhra Pradesh. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development*. 2018; 5:120.
10. Dirican M., Sarandol E., Ulukaya E., Tokullugil HA. Effects of smoking on serum lipid and lipoprotein concentrations and lecithin: cholesterol acyltransferase activity. *Journal of Medical Investigation*. 2019; 46:169-172.
11. Craig WY, Palomaki GE, Haddow JE. Cigarette smoking and serum lipid and lipoproteins concentrations - an analysis of published data. *BMJ*. 2019; 298: 781-88.
12. Harper's Illustrated Biochemistry-26th Edition- Robert K. Murray, MD, PhD, Daryl K. Granner, MD, Peter A. Mayes, PhD, DSc, Victor W. Rodwell, PhD.

13. Fedidat Raphael, Ariel A. Benson, Harold Jacob, & Eran Israeli. Gastrointestinal bleeding on anticoagulant therapy: Comparison of patients receiving vitamin K antagonists and non-vitamin K oral antagonists. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences*, 2022; 6(2): 2398–2413.